

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

Deliverable Report

WP2– Governance, Data Security and Ethics

Deliverable D2.4

STRONG AYA ethics report, with interim reports following ethics workshops

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STRONG-AYA Ethics report, with interim reports following Ethics workshops (year 1)

Publishable summary (max 1/2 page)

This deliverable is the report of the first meeting (3rd Nov 2023) of the STRONG-AYA Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Board (ERAB). The ERAB aims to provide the consortium with an independent view on the ethics and legal challenges as well as the mitigation actions planned or already implemented by the consortium. The ERAB is composed of four independent experts in ethics and/or legal aspects. The ERAB meets each year together with consortium representatives. This report has been approved by the four independent experts and by the project representatives who attended the meeting.

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2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
 2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
 3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
 4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
 5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
 6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
 7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
 8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
 9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
 10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
 11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
 12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
 13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
 14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
 15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)
- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
 - **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
 - **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
 - **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
 - **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
 - **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
MT	Management Team
ERAB	Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Committee

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. Infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

Defining AYAs with cancer as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis², their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴.

However, survival improvement in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors, which might be due to the fact that AYA have the highest absolute excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms⁵. AYA face some distinct challenges given that they do not belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of the scientific literature, these unique issues remain to be fully recognised and addressed by the European health systems and AYAs with cancer are frequently underserved. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the integrated paediatric ("patient/family-centred") care services versus dispersed ("disease- centered") adult oncology

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Review Group. Closing the gap: Research and Care Imperatives for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer. National Institute of Health, National Cancer Institute, and Livestrong Young Adult Alliance: Bethesda, MD, USA, 2006.

³ Trama A, Botta L, Steliarova-Foucher E. Cancer Burden in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Review of Epidemiological Evidence. *Cancer J* 2018; 24: 256-266

⁴ Trama A, Botta L, Foschi R et al. Survival of European adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer in 2000-07: population-based data from EURO-CARE-5. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: 896-906.

⁵ Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

⁶ Stark D, Bielack S, Brugieres L et al. Teenagers and young adults with cancer in Europe: from national programmes to a European integrated coordinated project. *European Journal of Cancer Care*, 25(3), 419-427.

⁷ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

services^{8,9,10}. Up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in society¹¹.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, given their challenges to sustain health insurance coverage¹². According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to Address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

To this aim, STRONG-AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

- 1. Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS) specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals.**

⁸ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE). *ESMO Open* 2021; 6: 100096.

⁹ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

¹⁰ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

¹¹ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

¹² Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

¹³ Saloustros E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. *Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health* 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁴ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

2. **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.
3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders,** in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

Implementing these project objectives are five work packages within the STRONG-AYA project:

- WP1: Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer and Data Collection (Lead: SOUTHAMPTON)
- WP2: Governance, Data Security and Ethics (Lead: EORTC)
- WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability (Lead: UNIMAAS)
- WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, Stakeholder and Patient involvement, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (Lead: E.C.O.)
- WP5: Scientific Coordination and Project Management (Lead: NKI)

STRONG-AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG-AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

4.2 Deliverable introduction

This deliverable is the report of the first meeting (3rd Nov 2023) of the STRONG-AYA Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Board (ERAB). The ERAB aims to provide the consortium with an independent view on the ethics and legal challenges as well as the mitigation actions planned or already implemented by the consortium. The ERAB is composed of four independent experts in ethics and/or legal aspects. The ERAB meets each year together with consortium representatives. This report has been approved by the four independent experts and by the project representatives who attended the meeting.

5 STRONG-AYA Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Board (ERAB) - Report of the 1st Meeting (virtual), 3 November 2023

5.1 Attendees:

- ERAB members
 - Francesco Tava, UK
 - Francis P. Crawley, BE
 - Matthias Braun, DE

- Santa Slokenberg, SE

- Consortium members
 - Darian Meacham, UNIMAAS
 - Leonard Wee, UNIMAAS
 - Lynn Hope, UOM
 - Marine Jacquemin, UNIMAAS
 - Simone Hanebaum, NKI
 - Stephane Lejeune, EORTC

5.2 Agenda

- Introduction to WP2 and the ERAB
- Project overview
- Feedback and recommendations from ERAB experts
- Q&A
- Wrap-up and closure

5.3 Main points of discussion

- 1) The goals and the main tasks of WP2 “Governance, data privacy and ethics” were explained. The ERAB operates under the responsibility of the WP2. A report will be generated from the discussions held during today’s ERAB meeting. This report will then be circulated for comment and eventual approval by the independent expert members of the ERAB.

- 2) What the consortium is expecting from ERAB members?
 - The ERAB is expected to help the consortium to go through the diverse challenges it faces, to help partners realize their responsibilities not only in term of compliance but also in a wider ethical perspective and, finally, to identify appropriate risk mitigation strategies. The ERAB should help the consortium step back and consider revising its focus when needed. The ERAB should help guide the consortium through advice, without providing the answers.

- 3) How have questions concerning children's rights been integrated in the Ethics and Governance activities of the project?
 - The project already has a focus on ethics and compliance, including data privacy aspects, but its perspective could be broader. The project is targeting Adolescent and Young Adult (AYA) cancer patients (15-39 years at primary cancer diagnosis), which is a broad patient population. The consortium should be attentive not to neglect specific issues pertaining to the more vulnerable subgroups of the targeted populations, such as the young adolescents.
 - The consortium needs to achieve more clarity regarding compliance with the protection of children’s interests: all European countries have some convention or guidance relevant to this topic. The requirements appear quite uniform. Concretely, the consortium should identify how to ensure the best interests of children are promoted and protected. It should ensure that children involved in project related activities are well informed about the project

and provided with proper consent. The consortium should carefully consider how it deals with such responsibilities relevant for the data holders at the national level as well as at the consortium and international levels within the federated infrastructure it is developing. The consortium will need to tackle these responsibilities in developing its ethics framework in relation to legal requirements (concretely, its code of conduct and the various agreements).

4) What kind of ethics review is needed in the project?

- In the federated model, patient-data remains in its original local database. Following a query made by an approved user, a specific algorithm will access all relevant participating databases to generate local models which will then be aggregated on the project's central server. It is only this final result which is visible to the approved user; at no point will they be able to see any patient-level data. The consortium will need to demonstrate that the infrastructure is secured. It further needs to obtain ethics approval for the envisaged data use and ensure the algorithms will address scientifically and ethically valid questions aligned with the project's purposes and the patients' interest. One of UNIMAAS's PhD students is currently examining how a federated learning approach can promote more ethical and legally compliant health data processing.
- The project activities will be developed on two levels, subject to different requirements: the local level and the European level. Locally, our consortium will help build, together with each local data owner (health institutions, hospitals...), project specific databases which will then be connected, via our European federated learning infrastructure. The project involves diverse data holders and datasets established in different countries whose local legal, ethical and societal rules and positions towards health data sharing in a federated learning system must be identified. To that end, the consortium conducted an extended survey collecting information from partners, including information related to data privacy, ethics, and standards.
- Each partner organisation contributing data is responsible for obtaining the applicable local EC approvals covering the use of the data in the project in line with available patient consent. Partners could use, as starting point, the ethics committee approval request prepared by NKI for its local Ethics Committee review.

5) How to balance patients' rights and project potential impact?

- The STRONG-AYA project seems to be compatible with the principles of the European Health Data Space in development. The consortium will need to consider specific issues arising in these new EU data and AI frameworks, including consent.
- There is a risk of impoverishing the data when using anonymisation. A pragmatic approach should be considered when addressing the need to reduce risks to patient privacy via data anonymisation and/or minimisation (removing physician name, location, date, etc.) and maintaining data usability for the project's purposes. The definition of the project's Core Outcome Set (data variables that should be collected) is important to identifying the key data that should be preserved. The consortium partners acknowledge that the different categories of end users (clinician, patient, decision makers, etc) may have different needs and expectations.
- It is important for the consortium to define the acceptable purposes for the use of the data within the project. A suitable ethical and legal framework needs to be in place and developed into a Code of Conduct (deliverable D2.2) and reflected in the various agreements that will be ratified by the consortium. The project stakeholder's engagement activities will enable the much-needed multistakeholder discussions.

6) What about the trade-off for patients?

- What could be the acceptable trade-off for a vulnerable population such AYA? When thinking about participating in a research project, patients may have to balance 1) perceived/potential benefits for their health, their self-esteem, etc. and the 2) the risk to their safety and privacy. It is the data controller who is responsible for data privacy compliance and risk management. The newly developed role of the 'data holder' also needs to be clarified in this context. From the patient's perspective, some degree of risk to their privacy may be of less important than the potential (beneficial) impact on their health or on the health of a patient group/population.
- AYA populations may have different concerns vis-à-vis privacy than older populations. Patients may be willing to accept a greater risk to privacy with the prospect of improved care. The risks for the patients in the STRONG-AYA context (secondary use of data via a federated infrastructure) need to be identified and, where possible, reduced or mitigated.
- The project should contribute to an understanding of what AYA patients are willing to accept in terms of data risks in a federated system, which privacy measures they expect, what data access frameworks are acceptable, and what they expect to see achieved for patients by the development and implementation of such a federated data system for AYA cancer research.
- Discussions with patient groups on how they understand the question of trade-offs and how these should be designed and communicated are important for the consortium going forward.

7) How do we ensure transparency towards patients?

- STRONG-AYA is built on the secondary use of data that were not collected from the patient directly for the project. The consortium does not have direct contact with most patients whose data would be involved in the project. For several reasons, it is not realistic to expect to re-contact the patient via the treating physician. However, there are different means that could be used. The first one is to disseminate public information via the project website explaining what the project is, what are the planned uses of the data, for which purposes the data is intended to be used, the project's impact on society, etc. In addition, the consortium could launch an information campaign via the patient partner Youth Cancer Europe and its communication channels, inviting people to contact the project to request specific information.

8) How do we safeguard data?

- Access to the federated data for system interrogation will not be open access. Users will need to be authorized and adhere to the project's user agreement. The type of research questions may present different risks of impact on patient rights. There will be different level of access for the different types of users/stakeholders. Each category of user/stakeholder will be allowed to pose different types of queries ranging from population description to questioning the efficacy of certain therapy in specific AYA patient subgroup.
- The assessment of the algorithms is one of the most important challenges for the consortium. The consortium needs to safeguard the interests of patients within the context of the responsibilities of the data controllers and data holders. The consortium could investigate user cases to understand better the potential risks and possibilities of such a federated patient data system for cancer research.

9) How does the project deal with patients' expectations?

- The consortium needs to understand patients expectations and to communicate clearly what the patients can expect from the project. The consortium needs to further define the specific

impact it expects to have on patients through such a federated data system for cancer research in AYA populations. The consortium should also investigate how it can integrate patient expectations in the project? How do we connect such considerations with the clinician in direct contact with the patient? Consultations with stakeholders' representatives have started and will be continued.

10) Wrap up

- The consortium will further work to prepare a robust infrastructure and suitable contractual framework that will enable the project to develop in compliance with applicable regulations and ethics standards taking into account the needs of the various stakeholders.
- The consortium values the ongoing iterative ERAB's guidance. The consortium is still discovering the issues and more will come along the project's implementation. This meeting represented the first discussion with the ERAB. The consortium requires more time to better understand the questions, collect concrete cases, and then reconvene with the ERAB for a more mature discussion. A follow-up meeting should be organised in 2024.

5.4 Actions

1. To confirm with partners that children participating to the project are properly informed and their rights are protected.
2. To clarify with partners what are the acceptable purposes for the use of the data within the project.
3. To discuss with patients the acceptable trade-offs.
4. To ensure that patients will be properly informed by the consortium about the project and the potential use of their data.
5. To define with partners the different types of research questions and which categories of users will be allowed to submit such queries.
6. To discuss with partners how we could capture patients' expectations and concretely integrate them to the project.